

Demonstration of multilevel multiply accumulate operations for AiMC using engineered a-IGZO transistors-based 2T1C gain cell arrays

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Abstract— We report on the first demonstration of multilevel multiply accumulate operations in 2T1C cell arrays based on amorphous IGZO TFTs for efficient analog in memory compute (AiMC) implementation. Device designs for the read and write transistors to meet the target specifications are discussed and implemented. Multilevel operations are realized thanks to the long retention time enabled by the ultra-low off-current ($< 1.5 \times 10^{-19}$ A/ μm) of the a-IGZO TFTs.

Keywords—IGZO, array, in-memory computing, multiply accumulate, retention, multilevel programming.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep learning has been applied in wide range of domains including speech recognition, translation, image processing. The growing application space drives the need for scaled, low-latency, and energy-efficient inference. Matrix-vector multiplications (MVM), which are fundamental to inference, can be implemented efficiently using Analog in-Memory Computing (AiMC).

A schematic of the generic AiMC architecture is shown in Fig 1 [1]. An array of compute cells stores the weight matrix ($w_{i,j}$). The activation signals from the input or the previous layer are converted to analog signals using DACs on the activation lines. The analog activation (act_i) is multiplied with the weight and each cell contributes $w_{i,j} \cdot act_i$ as a DC current or charge to the summation line. On the summation line, the output is the sum of all the contributions ($out_j = \sum w_{i,j} \cdot act_i$). The ADCs quantize the outputs to digital values which are passed on for further computations and then to next layer or buffer memory. Storing the weights as conductance of a memristive element requires clamping the summation line to a fixed reference level and is limited by the IR drop over the activation and summation lines [2]. Encoding the weight in the current level of current source-like elements (CSE), such as transistors operating in saturation or subthreshold, mitigates this and improves energy efficiency [1].

2T1C DRAM gain cells (schematic shown in Fig 2) can be implemented for compute cells [1]. The weight is stored on the storage node capacitor (C_{SN}) as voltage through the write transistor and the read transistor acts as the CSE. For a longer retention, ultra-low leakage is required. Smaller on-current of the read transistor lowers the IR drop on the summation line. Amorphous InGaZnO (a-IGZO) based TFTs can be tailored to meet both these requirements [3]. Moreover, the a-IGZO TFTs can be integrated in a BEOL compatible flow and can be 3D stacked, enabling dense arrays [4]. Simulations targeting AiMC applications with IGZO-TFTs have been reported in [5], and the DTCO framework for IGZO-based 2T1C has been discussed in [6]. However, no experimental multiply accumulate operations (MACs) in arrays of 2T1C cells have been demonstrated. In this work, we report the first experimental demonstration of MAC using a-IGZO-based 2T1C cell arrays.

Figure 1 General concept of MVM for AiMC [1].

Figure 2 A 2T1C DRAM gain cell. The read transistor acts as a current source-like element.

First, we discuss specifications for the write and the read transistors for a-IGZO-based 2T1C DRAM gain cell targeting AiMC applications. Then, device engineering to achieve these target specifications is described. We report excellent retention of the individual cell (> 130 s) and multilevel programming capability. The study is then extended to demonstrate MACs on arrays with multilevel weight encoding and activation.

II. DESIGN SPECIFICATIONS

A. Write transistor

The write transistor (assuming nominal width of 100 nm) must be able to program the weight in a reasonable voltage range with a reasonable periphery complexity, so write word line voltage (V_{WWL}) is preferably less than 1.8 V. To program a weight corresponding to 1 V on C_{SN} of 1fF in write time (t_{write}) of 10 ns for fast write condition, the on-current (I_{on}) of the write transistor should be > 100 nA (1 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$). Retention of analog states imposes stringent specifications on the acceptable voltage drop. The programmed weight changes as the storage node capacitor discharges due to leakage current through the capacitor or the transistors. To limit impact of change in weight on the accuracy of the neural network, $\Delta w_{i,j}$ of only 1% is allowed, i.e., $\Delta V_{SN} = 10$ mV for programmed weight of 1 V. Tolerating only 10 mV drop in 1 s (t_{ret}) on C_{SN} of 1 fF, the leakage current must be < 10 aA (10^{-16} A/ μm). Previously, we reported a-IGZO TFTs with ultra-low off

currents (I_{off}) on 300 mm wafer scale, which would meet this leakage criteria [7].

B. Read transistor

Current through the read transistor, which depends on the activation input and the stored weight in the C_{SN} , represents the multiply operation. For AiMC, I_{on} must be low, preferably < 100 nA ($1 \mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$) [1]. Further, dI/dV_{ds} should be low to reduce the impact of the summation line voltage on the current. The sensitivity to variation in the stored weight (i.e., its V_{g}) should also be low. A tolerance of 10 mV variation with less than 10% error is desired. For this, if the device is operated in saturation regime, $V_{\text{g}} - V_{\text{t}}$ must be > 100 mV; and if the device is operated in the subthreshold regime, subthreshold swing (SS) must be > 250 mV/dec.

The target specifications for the write and the read transistors are summarized in Fig 3. While the read transistor needs $I_{\text{on}} < 1 \mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$, the write transistor needs $I_{\text{on}} > 1 \mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$. Thus, different transistor designs are necessary to meet the specifications for write and read.

Assumption: $C_{\text{SN}} = 1$ fF, $t_{\text{write}} = 10$ ns, $\Delta V_{\text{write}} = 1$ V, $t_{\text{ret}} = 1$ s, $\Delta V_{\text{ret}} = 10$ mV

Figure 3 (Table) Target specifications and achieved median values for write and read transistor using the devices shown in the stack schematics. The respective transfer characteristics are shown.

C. Capacitor

C_{SN} is composed of the external capacitance, gate oxide capacitance of the read transistor and parasitic capacitance. Larger capacitance increases the retention time, making 2T1C implementation preferable over 2T0C implementation for lower power consumption in inference applications. Using the relation, $t_{\text{ret, capacitor}} = \frac{C\Delta V}{I_{\text{leak}}} = \frac{k\epsilon_0\Delta V}{t_{\text{ox}}J_{\text{leak}}}$, the leakage through the capacitor (J_{leak}) dominates the retention time if the leakage is attributed to the capacitor. The leakage through the capacitor must be much smaller than that through the a-IGZO transistor to benefit from the low I_{off} of the latter. For $t_{\text{ret, capacitor}} > 1000$ s, J_{leak} should be $< 10^{-11}$ A/cm².

III. DEVICE REALIZATION AND BENCHMARKING

A. Write transistor

Gate last device architecture with an oxygen tunnel module, 10 nm a-IGZO channel, and raised contacts of 10 nm CAAC-IGZO is used to achieve high I_{on} in the write transistor. The device fabrication is described in [3,8]. This is coupled with gate dielectric of 15 nm Al_2O_3 for lowering I_{off} and avoiding impact of gate stress on I_{off} [7]. The schematic of the write transistor along with achieved V_{t} (@ 100 pA \times W/L) and I_{on} (@ $V_{\text{g}} = V_{\text{t}} + 1$ V) values are shown in Fig 3. The variability in the devices measured across the 300 mm wafer is related to center-to-edge variations and the stochastic variability extracted from mismatch pairs (adjacently placed identical transistors) is very low [8]. The I_{off} evaluation is discussed later in Section III.D.

B. Read transistor

The read transistor is also integrated using the gate last scheme. However, in this case, 5 nm a-IGZO channel is deposited on SiN continuous buffer layer [9]. No post-process oxygen ambient anneal is required with the thinner channel [3]. 5 nm Al_2O_3 is used as the gate dielectric. The different criteria for the read transistor are met using this configuration, as listed in Fig 3.

C. Capacitor

TiN/ Al_2O_3 /TiN based MIM capacitors with varying Al_2O_3 thicknesses, 3 nm, 5 nm, 7 nm, and 9 nm, are tested for leakage current density using large capacitors of 200 $\mu\text{m} \times 200 \mu\text{m}$. The currents at 4 V can be reliably measured only up to 7 nm (not shown). Plot of $\ln(J_{\text{leak}} @ 4 \text{ V})$ with Al_2O_3 thickness in Fig 4 can be extrapolated to extract the thickness for achieving $J_{\text{leak}} < 10^{-11}$ A/cm², i.e. ~ 9 nm. For stored weight of 1 V across the capacitor, $J_{\text{leak}} \ll 10^{-11}$ A/cm² is expected for the 9 nm Al_2O_3 . Further, with this thickness, $C_{\text{ext}} > 1$ fF can be obtained for 400 nm \times 400 nm capacitor.

Figure 4 Plot of leakage current density (J_{leak}) through the TiN/ Al_2O_3 /TiN capacitors v/s Al_2O_3 thickness indicates that $J_{\text{leak}} \ll 10^{-11}$ A/cm² for 9 nm @ 1 V.

Figure 5 Evolution of V_{SN} with time for multiple devices (shown in different colors). Low device-to-device variability is observed across the 300 mm wafer. Initial V_{SN} -drop is related to the voltage swing on terminals. ($C_{\text{SN}} = 1.97$ fF, excluding parasitic)

D. 2T1C cell characterization

As the two transistors are engineered differently, they can ideally be integrated on different layers, leveraging on the 3D stackability of IGZO transistors and facilitating denser arrays [4]. For the purpose of multilevel MAC demonstration, different designs of the write and read transistors are not required. Therefore, in the following experiments, write and read transistor of similar design are used, i.e., the device engineered for the write transistor. The integration and layout of the 2T0C cell is described in [7]. For the 2T1C cell, we follow the same integration scheme, except that an additional external capacitor is integrated between the M1 and M2 metallization levels.

The methodology used for retention and off-current estimation is detailed in [7] and is outlined here. During the write operation, write transistor is switched on and the storage node is charged based on the bias on the WBL. Then write transistor is switched off for read operation and the read transistor current (I_{RBL}) evolution is monitored. From the polynomial fitting of $V_{SN}-I_{RBL}$, the evolution of V_{SN} is assessed. The V_{SN} evolution is fitted for exponential decay and t_{ret} (for ΔV_{SN} of 10 mV) and I_{off} are estimated as follows:

$$V_{SN} = V_{SN,init} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}$$

$$t_{ret} = \ln\left(\frac{V_{SN,init}}{V_{SN,init} - 0.01V}\right) \cdot \tau$$

$$I_{OFF} = \frac{V_{SN,init} \cdot C_{total}}{\tau \cdot W_{write}}$$

Figure 5 shows the evolution of V_{SN} for 10 2T1C cells measured across the 300 mm wafer. Note that the voltage at the beginning of the read operation is lower than that during the write. This voltage drop is attributed to the coupling capacitances lowering the bias with the voltage swings on the write transistor terminals [7]. The variability across the wafer is low for the single cells, and median I_{off} and t_{ret} are estimated to be 1.5×10^{-19} A/ μm and 130 s, respectively. Further programming optimization (write-verify scheme) may be done for more controlled device performance as described in [10].

Figure 6 Evolution of V_{SN} with time, when V_{WBL} is varied changing the stored weight, show distinct states even after 400 s. This multilevel operation is enabled by low I_{off} . I_{off} increases with V_{WBL} , but median is $< 2 \times 10^{-19}$ A/ μm . Devices similar to Fig 5 are used.

E. Multilevel programming in 2T1C cell

The low I_{off} enables long retention, creating the possibility of multilevel operation in these 2T1C cells, which is necessary for efficient AiMC application. The evolution of V_{SN} after being programmed to different weight levels by varying V_{WBL} between 0.4 V and 1.4 V is plotted in Fig 6, for 10 devices. Comparing the extracted retention time, shows longer retention for smaller stored weight, corresponding to a smaller I_{off} . This is attributed to the smaller bias across the write transistor terminals. The median t_{ret} is more than 100 s, with $I_{off} < 2 \times 10^{-19}$ A/ μm . The states are distinct even after 400 s.

Figure 7 Demonstration of MAC in a 2×2 array. Difference in sum of individual currents and I_{sum0} may be attributed to the parasitic. $(W/L)_{read,write} = 500 \text{ nm}/470 \text{ nm}$, $C_{SN} = 3.33 \text{ fF}$ (excluding parasitic).

Figure 8 Demonstration of MAC in 4×2 array (layout is extension of the 2×2 array). $(W/L)_{read,write} = 500 \text{ nm}/470 \text{ nm}$, $C_{SN} = 1.35 \text{ fF}$ (excluding parasitic).

IV. MULTIPLY ACCUMULATE OPERATION

We demonstrate multiply accumulate operations in arrays of 2×2 (schematic shown in Fig 7 along with cell notations) and 4×2 (schematic not shown), composed of the above a-IGZO-based 2T1C cells, emulating the AiMC weight matrix. These arrays do not have any peripheral circuit, we monitor the current through the summation line. One or more cells contributing to the summation line can be activated by applying appropriate bias on the respective activation lines.

Figure 7 shows the time evolution plot of the current measured on sum_0 (I_{sum0}) in the 2×2 array when the read transistors of $Cell_{0,0}$, $Cell_{1,0}$, as well as both simultaneously are activated using the biases tabulated in Fig 7. The stored

weights correspond to 1 V on both the above cells. The total current when act_0 and act_1 are simultaneously 0 V is almost equal to the sum of currents when act_0 and act_1 are individually 0 V. The summation line current depending on the input signals demonstrates the multiply accumulate operation using 2T1C cells with a-IGZO TFTs.

The above demonstration is extended further to the 4×2 arrays. Using similar scheme, the individual cells and their combinations are activated sequentially. The summation line currents are shown in Fig 8 along with the tabulated values.

Note that there is a small difference in the I_{sum0} when multiple cells are activated and the sum of their individual currents in both the 2×2 and 4×2 arrays. Given that this difference depends on the capacitance values, we speculate that this is related to circuit parasitic.

Next, we demonstrate analog weight matrix vector multiplication in the 4×2 array. The storage node is charged with V_{WBL} varied between 0.6 V and 1.2 V. The WBL of cells on the same summation line being connected in this array design, results in all the weights being programmed to the same value. With the activation line being switched between 0 V and 1 V, for the individual cells and the combinations, Fig 9 shows increase in the summation line current corresponding to the change in stored weights. Conversely, in Fig 10 changing the potential across the read transistors when activated by changing the summation line bias, also shows that the current scales accordingly.

With these measurements, we demonstrated that the 2T1C gain cells with IGZO can be successfully used for matrix vector multiplications in machine learning applications.

Figure 9 Multilevel MAC with C_{SN} programmed to different weights by varying V_{WBL} in 4×2 arrays. $(W/L)_{read,write} = 500 \text{ nm}/470 \text{ nm}$, $C_{SN} = 1.35 \text{ fF}$ (excluding parasitic).

Figure 10 Multilevel MAC with varied magnitude of activations by varying V_{sum0} is demonstrated in 4×2 array. $(W/L)_{read,write} = 500 \text{ nm}/470 \text{ nm}$, $C_{SN} = 1.35 \text{ fF}$ (excluding parasitic).

V. CONCLUSIONS

2T1C gain cells can be used for efficient implementation of AiMC as the read transistor can act as a current source element. However, stringent and divergent requirements are imposed on the write and the read transistors. We demonstrate that a-IGZO TFTs can be engineered to meet the specifications for both. Ultra-low off-current ($< 1.5 \times 10^{-19} \text{ A}/\mu\text{m}$) enables a long retention time for the 2T1C cell. This reduces the power consumption and benefits multilevel weight storage. We systematically characterize arrays of these 2T1C cells to demonstrate matrix vector multiplication. The multilevel accumulate operations for AiMC are reported with multilevel weights and activations. These results make the a-IGZO-based 2T1C cells compelling contender for AiMC applications.

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